

IMPACT DAMAGE CHARACTERISTICS OF J-2 THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES WITH "KEVLAR" ARAMID

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ABSTRACT

Two composite materials reinforced with Kevlar* aramid fabric were investigated for their impact damage and response characteristics. These composites were a toughened "Kevlar"/epoxy F155 (toughened epoxy matrix system) and "Kevlar"/J-2 (thermoplastic matrix system). Impact tests were conducted using a steel ball as impactor. Impact damage was inspected by X-ray and by optical microscope after sectioning the specimen through the impact site. Residual strengths were measured and plotted versus impact velocity. Behaviors of contact between the impactor and the composites were also investigated experimentally and the contact law was established. Dynamic response of the composite panels of both material systems was studied experimentally and by the finite element method. Overall, from these various aspects of impact behavior, these two composite systems appeared to have similar impact damage and response characteristics.

INTRODUCTION

Brittle epoxy matrix fiber composites are susceptible to impact damage. Under low velocity impact, the major forms of damage consist of matrix cracking and delamination. Delamination is the more critical, as it may cause significant reduction in compressive strength.

There are several methods for reducing impact-inflicted delamination in composite laminates. Sun and Rechak [1-2] placed tough adhesive film along interfaces of laminas to achieve greater toughness. Although the use of adhesive films is able to reduce delamination, it adds weight to the laminate. Moreover, the suppression of delamination may result in massive fiber breakage when impact velocity exceeds a certain threshold velocity. Therefore, Sun and Norman [3] proposed a new concept of using adhesive strips to toughen the lamina interface in a discrete manner. The discretely toughened laminate allows limited delamination to help absorb impact energy and prevent excessive fiber damage.

It was pointed out in [2] that delamination during impact was actually induced by matrix cracks in the lamina. Therefore, if matrix cracking is suppressed, delamination will also be suppressed. Fabric reinforcements and tough matrices will produce such results.

An amorphous polyamide copolymer designated J-2 has been developed recently by DuPont as a thermoplastic matrix for high performance fiber reinforced composites. This thermoplastic resin has good processibility, excellent toughness and good temperature capability. Previous evaluation showed that J-2 thermoplastic matrix reinforced with "Kevlar" aramid fibers offers attractive mechanical properties and processing characteristics [4].

The objective of this paper was to investigate the impact damage tolerance performance of composites reinforced with "Kevlar" aramid fabric. A commercial "toughened" epoxy composite with "Kevlar" aramid fabric was evaluated along with the J-2 thermoplastic composite for comparison.

SPECIMEN PREPARATION

Two types of composite systems were studied. The first, referred to as "Kevlar"/epoxy F155, has an

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epoxy matrix system with nominal 60% fiber volume. The reinforcing material used in this was "Kevlar" aramid fabric (type S-285, 4-harness satin with a toughened epoxy F155 resin). The second, referred to as "Kevlar"/J-2, is a thermoplastic composite system with nominal 60% fiber volume (coded T-5674-35; 8-harness satin, 36 inch wide, 8 x 8 ends/in; 7.93 oz/yd² basis weight). The 8-harness satin fabric was made with "Kevlar" aramid fiber melt impregnated with J-2 matrix resin [4].

Three 12 x 12 inch test panels of "Kevlar"/epoxy F155 were made with eight plies, all stacked with the zero degree fiber direction lying in the same direction. (The zero degree fiber direction was designated to be in the "wrap" direction of the rolls of both types of prepregs supplied.) Eight 9 x 9 inch composite test panels of "Kevlar"/J-2 thermoplastic were constructed with twelve plies, so that their thickness would be the same as the test panels of "Kevlar"/epoxy F155 (approximately .09 inches thick). All specimens used for the impact study measured approximately 1.375 x 6 inches, including the specimens used for residual strength tests and those used to measure the contact law. A specimen measuring 6 x 6 inches was used for the dynamic response tests.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

1 Impact and Residual Strength Tests

For impact damage tests, a 7/8 inch diameter steel ball was used as the impactor. A compressed air gun was used to produce impact velocities up to 22 m/s. The specimens were clamped at both ends to heavy stands leaving a 4-inch span. The impact site was aimed at the midspan of the specimen.

Two light emitting diodes and two photo detectors mounted on the gun barrel were used to determine the impactor velocity. When the impactor interrupted the first light beam, a pulse was generated to start the time counter. As the impactor cut the second light beam, another pulse was generated to stop the time counter. The velocity of the impactor is obtained by dividing the distance between the two light emitting diodes by the time registered on the counter.

A 3-point bending test was employed to measure the residual bending strength of a specimen after impact. An end-to-end span of 3 inches was used. This short span was chosen in order to avoid excessive deflections. The impact point was placed right under the load application.

In order to see the damage sustained during impact, specimens were examined with X-rays. A dye penetrant (1,4 diiodobutane) was injected into a tiny hole drilled through the thickness of the specimen at the impact center. The diiodobutane penetrated the delaminated and cracked regions and showed up as dark areas in the X-ray radiographs.

After being X-rayed, the specimens were sectioned longitudinally through the impact center. The longitudinal edge (through the impact center) was then polished on several progressively finer polishing wheels to obtain a smooth surface to examine under the microscope. Microphotographs of the polished edge were taken at 25x.

2 Static and Dynamic Contact Tests

A static indentation set-up described in [5] was used for the indentation test. The specimen was clamped at both ends with a 2-inch span. The indenter had a spherical cap 0.5 inch in diameter. A linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) mounted on a "C" bracket fixed to the loading shaft allowed the relative movement between the indenter and the specimen to be recorded. The output of LVDT and strain indicator were fed into an X-Y recorder so that a continuous force-indentation curve was obtained.

A 6 by 6 inch panel of each composite system was used in studying the dynamic contact behavior. To avoid damage in the panel so that it could be repeatedly used in the experiment, a very low impact velocity (2 m/s) was considered. A pendulum with a 0.5-inch diameter steel ball was used as the impactor.

To measure the dynamic strain histories, three dynamic strain gages were mounted on the panel. Gage #1 was mounted at the center of the plate; gage #2 was mounted 1 inch away from gage #1 in the 0°-direction; and gage #3 was located 1 inch away from gage #1 in the 90°-direction. The strain gages were wired to Wheatstone bridges. The output of the Wheatstone bridges was fed into amplifiers and from there to a signal digitizer. The data recorded by the digitizer was sent to a computer for storage and

plotting.

IMPACT DAMAGE

Three methods were employed to evaluate impact damage, i.e., measuring residual strength after impact, inspecting internal damage by X-ray, and visually inspecting the impact site cross-section.

1 Residual Strength

The residual bending strength was calculated with the bending equation

$$\sigma = \frac{My}{I} \quad (1)$$

where M is the bending moment at mid-span, y is one-half the thickness of the specimen, and I is the cross-section moment of inertia.

Figure 1 presents the residual strengths for both material systems. For both material systems, the 0° and 90° specimens exhibited approximately the same residual strengths. Thus, they were combined as one data group in this plot.

Fig. 1 Residual bending strength versus impact velocity.

Note that the composite specimens of epoxy F155 and J-2 exhibit the same residual strength characteristics. Both exhibit an initial loss of strength at an impact velocity of about 15 meters per second, and a sharp decrease in residual strength at an impact velocity between 15 and 20 m/s. This indicates that at velocities greater than 15 m/s extensive fiber damage would have occurred. This behavior is similar to that of graphite/epoxy laminates containing interface-toughening adhesive films as observed in [1].

Based on the slight difference between the residual strengths of the two material systems as indicated by Fig. 1, we note that the thermoplastic composite of J-2 seems able to retain its strength better than the composite of F155 epoxy for velocities up to 15 m/s. Beyond 20 m/s, the residual strength of the thermoplastic composite of J-2 appears to drop below the composite of F155 epoxy indicating more severe fiber damage. This is an indication that the thermoplastic composite of J-2 is tougher than the composite of F155 epoxy.

2 X-ray Inspection

From the residual strength plots, it is evident that the specimens of both material systems begin to suffer impact damage at approximately 15 m/s. At 20 m/s, the specimens retain almost no strength. For this reason, we selected three impact velocities, 15, 17.5, and 20 m/s, for post impact X-ray inspection.

Figures 2 and 3 present the typical X-ray radiographs taken of the composite specimens of "Kevlar"/epoxy F155 and J-2, respectively. Both types of specimens show very slight damage at 15 m/s. However, at 20 m/s impact, the thermoplastic composite of J-2 exhibits similar damage. This finding is consistent with the residual strength results.

impact velocity = 15.0 meters per second

impact velocity = 15.0 meters per second

impact velocity = 20.0 meters per second

impact velocity = 20.0 meters per second

Fig. 2 X-ray radiographs of composite of "Kevlar"/epoxy F155.

Fig. 3 X-ray radiographs of composite of "Kevlar"/J-2.

3 Microscopic Inspection

At an impact velocity of 17.5 m/s, the specimen of "Kevlar"/epoxy F155 showed evidence of internal matrix cracking in the fiber bundle on the top ply where the ball struck. In the lowest plies of the specimen, a bending crack extends through several plies of the specimen. This crack extends through one entire longitudinal fiber bundle (creating fiber breakage) and appears to extend part-way into the next longitudinal fiber bundle. Matrix cracks or delamination appear along the interfaces of some of the fiber bundles, especially in the lower plies. The composite specimen of J-2 impacted at 17.5 m/s also shows signs of fiber breakage in the extreme lower plies of the specimen. The lowest ply on this specimen had fibers lying longitudinally at the impact center. These were broken by the bending stress. The bending crack extends through some transverse fibers and then through another bundle of longitudinal fibers (more fiber breakage). The amount of fiber breakage seems to be about the same for both the composite specimens of F155 and of J-2. These observations are consistent with the residual strength test results. In those tests, residual strength dropped off considerably at an impact velocity of 17.5 m/s, indicating the onset of fiber breakage.

Fiber breakage and delamination are more severe at an impact velocity of 20 m/s for the specimen of "Kevlar"/epoxy F155. The bending crack resulting from bending stress follows a multi-path course through many of the lower plies in the specimen. Fiber breakage resulting from this crack going through longitudinal fiber bundles is seen as far up as plies in the center of the laminate. Note that delamination is still rather limited to the immediate vicinity of the impact center. The composite specimen of J-2 impacted at 20 m/s also displayed a bending crack through several of the lower plies of the specimen. However, it does not appear to extend as far into the specimen as with the specimen of "Kevlar"/epoxy F155. Delamination is certainly more severe, however, as the lowest ply of this specimen is delaminated along the entire length of the photograph. Both the composite specimens of epoxy F155 and J-2 appear to be severely damaged near the impact center at an impact velocity of 20 m/s. This is in agreement with the residual strength tests, as residual strength was very low at this velocity.

CONTACT BEHAVIOR

Contact behavior is usually described by the contact law which relates contact force and indentation. This relation is nonlinear making the dynamic impact problem nonlinear even if the target material is linearly elastic.

An experimental procedure for determining the contact law for an elastic sphere in contact with flat laminates has been proposed by Yang and Sun [5]. The procedure involves loading, unloading, and then reloading a laminate specimen. The experimental data is then used to fit contact laws given by

$$\text{Loading} \quad F = k\alpha^n \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Unloading} \quad F = F_m [(\alpha - \alpha_o) / (\alpha_m - \alpha_o)]^q \quad (3)$$

where F is contact force, α is indentation, F_m and α_m indicate the force and indentation at which unloading begins, k is the contact rigidity, α_o is the permanent indentation, and n and q are coefficients to be determined based on experimental data. In [5] it was found that $n = 1.5$ and $q = 2.5$ were suitable for epoxy-based fiber composites.

Table 1 lists all the values of the contact rigidity k with $n = 1.5$ power law fit. It is evident that both material systems have basically the same contact rigidity.

Table 1 Contact rigidities.

panel type	test no.	n	k	average k
"Kevlar"/epoxy F155	1	1.5	6.43×10^5	6.09×10^5
	2	1.5	5.22×10^5	
	3	1.5	6.61×10^5	
"Kevlar"/J-2	1	1.5	5.48×10^5	5.19×10^5
	2	1.5	4.33×10^5	
	3	1.5	5.77×10^5	

For the unloading curve, the only unknown is the permanent indentation α_o if we choose $q = 2.5$. The value of α_o is a function of α_m (or F_m). From the indentation test data, we plot α_o versus α_m and fit them in the form

$$\alpha_o = s_p (\alpha_m - \alpha_p) \quad (4)$$

where α_p may be regarded as the elastic limit of indentation below which no permanent indentation occurs. For the thermoplastic composite of J-2,

$$s_p = 0.336 \quad , \quad \alpha_p = 1.38 \times 10^{-3} \text{ inch} \quad (5)$$

For composite of F155 epoxy,

$$s_p = 0.137 \quad , \quad \alpha_p = 1.41 \times 10^{-3} \text{ inch} \quad (6)$$

Using Eq. (3) together with Eqs. (4-6), typical unloading curves for the "Kevlar"/epoxy F155 and J-2 systems are presented in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively. The predicted unloading curves agree with the experimental results quite well at low load levels. At higher levels of contact force, a larger value of q seems to be more suitable.

Fig. 4 Typical unloading curves for composite of "Kevlar"/epoxy F155.

Fig. 5 Typical unloading curves for composite of "Kevlar"/J-2.

From the results given by Eqs. (5-6), we can say that the thermoplastic composite of J-2 is more ductile, i.e., for a given impact force, the permanent dent left on this composite should be greater than that on the composite of F155 epoxy.

DYNAMIC RESPONSE

Low velocity impact tests were performed using a 6 x 6 inch panel and a 1/2 inch ball with pendulum setup as described previously. The panel was hung with two strings to produce unconstrained boundary conditions. The impact velocity was 2 m/s.

Dynamic impact analysis was performed using finite element method in conjunction with the contact law. The plate finite element used in this study was a quadrilateral isoparametric element with nine nodes based on Mindlin plate theory [6].

Typical strain histories at strain gages #1 and #2 on "Kevlar"/epoxy J-2 are shown in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively. The agreement between the finite element solutions and experimental results is fairly good. This indicates that the contact law, although measured statically, is adequate in dynamic analysis.

Fig. 6 Dynamic strain history response at gage #1 in the "Kevlar"/J-2 panel.

Fig. 7 Dynamic strain history response at gage #2 in the "Kevlar"/J-2 panel.

CONCLUSION

From the results of this study, we conclude that both thermoplastic composite of J-2 and toughened composite material of F155 epoxy have similar impact tolerance characteristics. Since both are reinforced by "Kevlar" aramid fabrics, the matrix toughnesses in these composites are dominated by the fabrics, and, thus, the difference in matrix toughness cannot be clearly displayed by the composites. However, from their impact residual strength behaviors, there is indication that composite of "Kevlar"/J-2 may be slightly tougher than composite of "Kevlar"/epoxy F155 in resisting impact loading.

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